

Differential refractometry as a new technique for determination of stoichiometry and stability constants of metal complexes

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Abstract : A general method using refractometric and differential refractometric techniques has been developed to evaluate the stoichiometry and stability constants of metal-ligand complexes. The technique has been verified on the complexation of Cu^{2+} with phenoxyacetic acid (PAA), 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) and 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4,5-T). This newly developed technique has been found to be compatible with potentiometric and spectrophotometric methods when applied to the complexation of model amino acids, such as, phenylalanine (phe), tyrosine (tyr), tryptophan (trp) and some dipeptides, such as, phen-tyr, and trp-tyr, in solution. Calculated stoichiometry and stability constants of these metal complex equilibria either by simple refractometric method or by differential refractometric method are comparable to those obtained by spectrophotometric and potentiometric techniques.

Keywords : Refractive index, differential refractometry, stability constant.

In the present investigation general refractometric, differential refractometric and spectrophotometric techniques have been developed to evaluate the stoichiometry and stability constants of binary metal complexes of Cu^{2+} with phenoxy acids, amino acids and dipeptides as model ligands.

Theoretical :

The refractometric and differential refractometric techniques are based on the theory that the refractive index, n , of a solution is proportional to the molar refraction and depends on concentration¹. The coefficient of refraction of a mixture of two solutions, if the components react with each other, has no longer the theoretical value computed from the values of individual solution by addition. The measured deviation, Δn , expressed by, $\Delta n = n_{\text{theo}} - n_{\text{exp}}$, may be plotted against molar ratio of the components to get stoichiometry and stability constants of metal complexes.

This method has been modified because the theoretical values are evaluated from the density and concentrations of solutions of the parent components which may introduce errors in the evaluation of refractive index due to complex in solution.

For the equilibrium,

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a'-x)(b'-2x)^2} \quad (1)$$

where a , a' and b , b' are the initial concentrations of the metal and ligand in two different series of experiments; x is the equilibrium concentration of the complex corresponding to the same value of Δn .

On rearranging, eq. (1) takes the form,

$$Ax^2 + Bx + C = 0 \quad (2)$$

where,

$$A = 4\{(a+b) - (a'+b')\};$$

$$B = b'^2 - b^2 + 4(a'b' - ab); C = ab^2 - a'b'^2$$

Thus, on getting x , eq. (1) may be solved for K .

The refraction per cm^3 due to complex ($\Delta\Omega T_{\text{ML}}$) can be calculated using the following equation,

$$10^3 (\phi - \phi_{\text{L}}) - \Omega_{\text{M}} T_{\text{M}}^0 = 6000 (n - n_{\text{L}})n_{\text{L}}/(n_{\text{L}}^2 + 2)^2 - \Omega_{\text{M}} T_{\text{M}}^0 = \Delta\Omega T_{\text{ML}} \quad (3)$$

where $\Omega_{\text{M}} T_{\text{M}}^0$ is defined as follows :

$$\Omega_{\text{M}} T_{\text{M}}^0 = 10^3 (\phi_{\text{M}} - \phi_0) = 6000 (n_{\text{M}} - n_0)n_0/(n_0^2 + 2)^2 \quad (4)$$

The quantity Ω_j for j -th solute is defined as $\Omega_j = R_j - V_j \phi_0$, where R_j is apparent molar refraction and V_j the apparent molar volume of the j -th solute².

The refraction per cm^3 of solvent (ϕ_0), metal ion (ϕ_{M}),

ligand (ϕ_L) and solution (ϕ) may be calculated as follows :

$$\phi_0 = (n_0^2 - 1)/(n_0^2 + 2); \phi_M = (n_M^2 - 1)/(n_M^2 + 2)$$

$$\phi_L = (n_L^2 - 1)/(n_L^2 + 2); \text{ and } \phi = (n^2 - 1)/(n^2 + 2)$$

where n_0 , n_M , n_L and n are the refractive indices of solvent, metal, ligand and solution (metal + ligand). From the two successive plots for two series of measurements with different initial concentrations of metal and ligand, it may be assumed that the concentration of the complex is the same for the same value of refraction per cm^3 . Hence, the value of stability constant may be evaluated from the same relation as described above (eqs. 1 and 2).

Eqs. (1) and (2) can also be applied for the calculation of equilibrium constant by spectrophotometric technique assuming the concentration of the complex to be the same at the same absorbance in two systems of measurements having different initial concentrations of metal and ligand.

Materials and methods :

Ligands, α -amino acids, dipeptides, PAA; 2,4-D, 2,4,5-T, and cupric nitrate used were obtained from Fluka AG, Switzerland. The sodium salts of these acids for refractometric measurements have been prepared by treating equimolar amounts of NaHCO_3 with above mentioned acids. The solutions were prepared in 70% aq. dioxan (v/v) except for 2,4,5-T or its sodium salt due to solubility reasons for which a 70% aq. methanol (v/v) was used.

The refractive indices and spectrophotometric measurements have been carried out on Bausch and Lomb refractometer with an accuracy of ± 0.00002 and Beckman-DU spectrophotometer, respectively, at 25 ± 0.1 °C. The refractive indices measurements were made for Cu^{2+} , ligand and solutions having 1 : 4, 1 : 3, 1 : 2, 2 : 3, 1 : 1, 3 : 2, metal-ligand ratios (keeping the total volume 10 ml).

Results and discussion

From the experimental values of refractive indices (n_{exp}) of the metal-ligand solutions, the values of Δn , have been obtained by using the following relation

$$\Delta n = n_{\text{theo}} - n_{\text{exp}} \tag{5}$$

where n_{theo} is defined by the following relation

$$n_{\text{theo}} = \frac{pd_1.n_1 + q.d_2.n_2}{pd_1 + q.d_2} \tag{6}$$

where, n_1 , n_2 = the refractive indices of the solutions; d_1 , d_2 = their densities and p , q = the volumes of the two solutions.

The plots Δn vs molar ratios of the components have been made which have shown maxima at 1 : 2 composition irrespective of the nature of ligand considered. The points on the abscissa corresponding to actual (Δn_1) and

ideal (Δn_2) have been used to calculate the degree of dissociation (α) of the complex and stability constant using eqs. (7) and (8)

$$\alpha = \frac{\Delta n_2 - \Delta n_1}{\Delta n_2} \tag{7}$$

and,

$$K = \frac{1 - \alpha}{\alpha^2.C} \tag{8}$$

where C is the total initial concentration of the complex in solution.

Above method has been modified without using α for calculating the stability constants by plotting Δn values against molar ratio for two initial concentrations of each of Cu^{2+} and a ligand (Fig. 1). From the two curves, the concentration of the complex corresponding to the same value of Δn and hence the stability constants (Table 1) have been computed using eqs. (1) and (2).

Differential refractometric method :

The plots of $\Delta\Omega T_{ML}$ vs molar ratios with negative deviation show that the complex is less polar than the components. The calculation of stability constants have been made in the same way by plotting $\Delta\Omega T_{ML}$ against molar ratio of the components for two different initial concentrations as in the case of refractometric method. For the same value of refraction per cm^3 ($\Delta\Omega T_{ML}$) due to complex, its concentration has been assumed to be the same. Hence, from the knowledge of two initial concentrations of metal and ligand, the values of K have been calculated by using eqs. (1) and (2).

The refractometry and differential refractometry techniques have proved to be useful to investigate metal ligand

Fig. 1. Plots of Δn vs molar ratio of solutes indicating 1 : 2 stoichiometry of Cu^{2+} -2,4-D complex : (A) $[\text{Cu}^{2+}] = [\text{L}^-] = 2 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$, (B) $[\text{Cu}^{2+}] = [\text{L}^-] = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$.

Table 1. Stability constants^a of Cu²⁺ complexes with phenoxyacetic acids, amino acids and dipeptides

System	log β				
	Refractometric		Differential refractometric	Spectrophotometric	Potentiometric
	From eq. (1)	From eq. (7)	From eq. (1)	From eq. (1)	(Ref. 3)
Cu ²⁺ -PAA	5.60	5.80	5.85	5.49	6.17
Cu ²⁺ -2,4-D	5.07	5.32	5.72	5.28	6.09
Cu ²⁺ -2,4,5-T	4.98	5.12	5.66	5.02	5.92
Cu ²⁺ -try	13.76	13.89	14.55	14.25	14.98
Cu ²⁺ -phe	13.65	13.78	14.27	13.98	14.50
Cu ²⁺ -tyr	13.28	13.58	14.20	13.87	14.45
Cu ²⁺ -phe-tyr	10.48	10.54	11.28	10.78	11.51
Cu ²⁺ -phe-trp	10.64	10.78	11.98	10.99	12.38
Cu ²⁺ -trp-tyr	9.45	9.79	10.38	9.54	10.63

^aStandard error = ± 0.02 .

complex equilibria and the results obtained are comparable to those obtained by other methods³ (Table 1).

Spectrophotometric method :

Mixtures containing varying proportions of a ligand and Cu²⁺ were prepared and absorbance was measured at different wavelengths. Optical density observations have shown that maximum absorption occurs in all the mixtures at 660 nm. It may be said, therefore, that only one complex is formed between Cu²⁺ and PAA or 2,4-D.

The method of continuous variation has been used keeping total volume 25 ml. A large number of experiments using equimolar and non-equimolar solutions in the pH range 3.5–4.5, were employed and the measurements were done at two different wavelengths, 640 and 660 nm. As seen from the representative plot a peak at ratio 1 : 2 of the reactants has shown 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the complex.

The absorbance of mixtures containing 0.05 M of Cu²⁺ and 0.1 M PAA or 2,4-D at various pH, were measured at different wavelengths. It is evident that λ_{\max} lies at 660 nm between pH 3.50 to 5, showing that the complex is stable in this pH range.

The method of continuous variation has been used with equimolar solutions (total volume 25 ml) and the absorbance of the mixtures has been measured at 660 nm. The absorbances have been plotted against $[Cu^{2+}] / [Cu^{2+}] + [L^-]$ (Fig. 2) for three different initial concentrations. The solutions of PAA and 2,4-D were colourless, hence the colour of the mixture is due to Cu²⁺ and the complex formed. With progressive addition of PAA or 2,4-D, [Cu²⁺] decreases and in the descending portions of the curves, the contribution of free Cu²⁺ to the absorbance of the mixture is negligible. The observed absorbance, therefore, has been attributed to be due to the colour of the complex alone. A horizontal line at absorbance 0.4 (Fig. 2) has been drawn parallel to the molar ratio axis and taking two points at the two curves, the value of overall stability constant, for the equilibrium $Cu^{2+} + 2L^- \rightleftharpoons CuL_2$ has been calculated using eq. (2) at the same absorbance for the two curves.

Fig. 2. Plots of absorbance against $[Cu^{2+}] / [Cu^{2+}] + [L^-]$: (A) $[Cu^{2+}] = [L^-] = 4 \times 10^{-1} M$, (B) $[Cu^{2+}] = [L^-] = 4 \times 10^{-1} M$, (C) $[Cu^{2+}] = [L^-] = 1 \times 10^{-1} M$.

In conclusion, the techniques like, refractometric, differential refractometric and spectrophotometric have been developed to obtain stoichiometry and stability constants of metal complexes with better approximations. These techniques may also be useful in the study of mixed-ligand complex equilibria in solution.

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